

The luminous flux through a ball with absorption

Harald Schröer

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We look a point source Q with the luminous intensity I and a ball with the distance r (see figure).

R = radius of the ball β = angle of inclination

m = absorption coefficient of the medium

$$\cos \alpha_{max} = \frac{R}{r}$$

law of sines:

$$\frac{\sin(180^\circ - \beta)}{r} = \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha}} \quad (1)$$

illumination:

$$E(\alpha) = \frac{I}{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha} \cdot e^{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha} \cdot (-m)}$$

For the luminous flux Φ through the ball follows:

$$\Phi = 2\pi R \cdot \int_0^{\alpha_{max}} R \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot E(\alpha) \cdot \cos \beta(\alpha) d\alpha$$

It will be integrated in circles. The R in front of the integral sign is the Gram determinant's root of the ball (the derivation comes later).

With (1) follows because of $\sin(180^\circ - \beta) = \sin \beta$.

$$\sin \beta = \frac{r \sin \alpha}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha}}$$

$$\cos \beta = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \beta}$$

we conclude:

$$\cos \beta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r^2 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha}{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha}}$$

We obtain at last:

$$\Phi = 2\pi R^2 \cdot I \cdot \int_0^{\alpha_{max}} \frac{\sin \alpha \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{r^2 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha}{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha}}}{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha} \cdot e^{-m \cdot \sqrt{r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \alpha}} d\alpha$$

$$\text{with } \alpha_{max} = \arccos\left(\frac{R}{r}\right) \quad (2)$$

This integral cannot be calculated for $m \neq 0$ or $m = 0$.

Now we still determine the Gram determinant g_c of the metric tensor (see Forster [1] §3 and §14) in relation to the ball's integration: It will be shown that $\sqrt{g_c} = R$.

$$\vec{c}(\alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R \sin \alpha \\ 0 \\ R \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D\vec{c} = \begin{pmatrix} R \cos \alpha \\ 0 \\ -R \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(D\vec{c})^T = (R \cos \alpha, 0, -R \sin \alpha)$$

$$g_c = \det [(D\vec{c})^T \cdot (D\vec{c})]$$

$$= \det \left[(R \cos \alpha, 0, -R \sin \alpha) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} R \cos \alpha \\ 0 \\ -R \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

$$= \det [R^2 \cos^2 \alpha + R^2 \sin^2 \alpha] = R^2$$

$\sqrt{g_c} = R$ is the searched factor. We calculate an example with $I=1$ Candela and $R=1$ metre. The wavelength shall be 435 nanometres. Then the absorption coefficient of air is $0.00003 \text{ metre}^{-1}$. We get an approximation with:

$$\Phi \approx \pi \cdot I \cdot \frac{R^2}{r^2}$$

The result is the following table, there is a comparison between the exact formula and the approximation. The distance r is presented in metre, the luminous flux in Lumen.

r	luminous flux (exact)	luminous flux (approximation)
2	0.84174	0.78540
3	0.35931	0.34907
4	0.19949	0.19635
5	0.12693	0.12566
6	0.08787	0.08727
7	0.06443	0.06411
8	0.04927	0.04909
9	0.03890	0.03879
10	0.03149	0.03142

The approximation is more accurate with increasing r .

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001